

Solubility Product of Barium Oxalate at a Number of Temperatures

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Solubility product of Barium Oxalate has been measured at 25°, 35°, 45°, 55°, 65° and 75° by standard volumetric methods and the values of $7 + \log K_{sp}$ at the respective temperatures have been found to be 0.339, 0.461, 0.490, 0.515, 0.549 and 0.558.

The heat of solution in the above range of temperature is positive and is 5100, 1300, 1200, 2000, and 500 cal. at 30°, 40°, 50°, 60° and 70°. The big change in ΔH suggests change in the hydration of the solid phase.

Solubility product of Barium Oxalate defined as ${}^a\text{Ba}^{2+} \times {}^a\text{X}^{2-} = K_{sp}$ is not known accurately. Kohlrausch measured the solubility of $\text{BaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{BaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 3\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{BaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{XH}_2\text{O}$ between temperatures 2.07° to 33.73° conductometrically¹. Groschuff² measured the solubility of the three hydrates at different temperatures ranging between 0° to 100°. Cantoni and Diotalevi³ obtained higher values for the solubilities of Barium Oxalate than the above two workers. Scholder⁴ found the solubility of $\text{BaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 18° conductometrically.

Direct determination of solubility of Barium Oxalate is possible in presence of HClO_4 which was deliberately added to increase solubility and prevent hydrolysis of Oxalate ion ($\text{X}^{2-} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{HX}^- + \text{OH}^-$), the calculations become a little complicated. Since we needed the values of K_{sp} at a number of temperatures, it was decided to determine the solubility product by measuring the solubility by standard volumetric methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

25 g. of A.R. $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in 200 ml. of double distilled water. To this 1 ml. of 11 (N) HCl was added and the solution was heated to boiling. Saturated ammonium oxalate solution prepared from A.R. sample was then added to this in slight excess. The precipitate was washed several times with double distilled water till free from chloride and then twice with 95% alcohol and dried at 120°. It was then kept in loosely stoppered bottles at ordinary temperatures. The Barium content of the Oxalate was estimated with standard E.D.T.A. solution by usual method⁵. The Oxalate content was estimated by titrating against standard KMnO_4 solution⁷. The product on analysis corresponded to $\text{BaX} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Solubility of Barium Oxalate was measured at 25°, 35°, 45°, 55°, 65° and 75°. At every temperature eight or nine set of readings were taken to cover the range upto $\mu = 0.1$. For each set 1 ml. of 0.1 N HClO_4 , requisite quantity of 0.5 M KCl was taken in a 250 ml. measuring flask. Double distilled water was added to make the volume 250 ml. This

solution was transferred in a dry conical flask. Solid $\text{BaX} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was now added and the solution was stirred vigorously with a magnetic stirrer for 3 hr in an air thermostat controlled to $\pm 0.05^\circ$. It was confirmed in some cases that stirring for 2 hr more did not make any difference. The solution was filtered in the thermostat itself through a G3 sintered glass funnel. Fifty or hundred ml. of the solution was titrated against standard KMnO_4 solution (about $0.02N$) by usual method⁷. The KMnO_4 consumed corresponded to the amount of oxalate and bioxalate taken together, present in solution and so it corresponded to the amount of Ba. pH of the solution was measured in a Beckmann pH meter reading correct to 0.1 but by eye estimation readings could be taken correct to 0.05 units.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Scholder⁴ has measured the conductance of a saturated solution of $\text{BaX} \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as well as the solution obtained by diluting the saturated solution. He has found increase in equivalent conductance. Money and Davies⁵ have calculated the dissociation constant of BaX based on this data. At 18° the degree of dissociation was found to be 0.936. The oxalate ion will react with water $\text{X}^{2-} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{HX}^- + \text{OH}^-$. The OH^- has a high equivalent conductance. The increase in equivalent conductance may be due to this hydrolysis. So we have assumed Barium Oxalate in solution to be completely dissociated. In presence of HClO_4 the following equations hold good.

$$\underset{c}{[\text{Ba}^{2+}]} = \underset{c_1}{[\text{X}^{2-}]} + [\text{HX}^-] \quad \dots (1)$$

$$[\text{HClO}_4]_T = [\text{HX}^-] + [\text{H}^+] \quad \dots (2)$$

So,

$$[\text{HX}^-] = c_1 = [\text{HClO}_4]_T - [\text{H}^+]$$

and,

$$[\text{X}^{2-}] = c - c_1$$

The ionic strength of the solution,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= 2[\text{Ba}^{2+}] + 2[\text{X}^{2-}] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{HX}^-] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{H}^+] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{ClO}_4^-] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{K}^+] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{Cl}^-] \\ &= 2[\text{Ba}^{2+}] + 2[\text{X}^{2-}] + [\text{HClO}_4]_T + [\text{KCl}]_T \\ &= 4[\text{Ba}^{2+}] - 2[\text{HX}^-] + [\text{HClO}_4]_T + [\text{KCl}]_T \quad \dots (3) \end{aligned}$$

Here, $[\text{HClO}_4]_T$ = stoichiometric concentration of HClO_4 and $[\text{KCl}]_T$ = stoichiometric concentration of KCl . In equation (3), $[\text{KCl}]_T$ and $[\text{HClO}_4]_T$ are known from the amount of HClO_4 and KCl added to the solution. $[\text{Ba}^{2+}]$ is known as explained earlier, the value of $[\text{H}^+]$ is found from pH measurements and the value of $[\text{HX}^-]$ is known from equation (2). The activity coefficient of H^+ was taken to be equal to the mean activity coefficient of HCl at the respective ionic strength. The ionic strength was computed from equation (3) above.

$$K_{sp} = a_{\text{Ba}^{2+}} \times a_{\text{X}^{2-}} = [\text{Ba}^{2+}][\text{X}^{2-}] \cdot f_2^+ \cdot f_2^- \quad \dots (4)$$

Using Debye-Hückel-Bronsted equation⁸

$$\log f = -AZ^2\sqrt{\mu} + B\mu \quad \dots (5)$$

We get,

$$\log K_{sp} = \log[Ba^{2+}] + \log[X^{2-}] - 8A\sqrt{\mu} + 2\beta\mu$$

so,

$$\log[Ba^{2+}] + \log[X^{2-}] - 8A\sqrt{\mu} = \log K_{sp} - B\mu \quad \dots (6)$$

or,

$$\log c(c-c_1) - 8A\sqrt{\mu} = \log K_{sp} - B\mu \quad \dots (7a)$$

A plot of L.H.S. against μ gives a straight line curve and the intercept on the ordinate gives $\log K_{sp}$. To save space detailed experimental result at 35° only is given in Table 1 below. When $\log c(c-c_1) - 8A\sqrt{\mu}$ as given in column 9 was plotted against μ as given in column 5, a straight line curve was obtained with an intercept on the ordinate equal to $\bar{7}\cdot461$. This value of $\log K_{sp}$ was also computed by the method of least squares. Likewise at other temperatures also the value of $\log K_{sp}$ was found out.

TABLE 1

Variation of solubility of BaX with ionic strength at 35°: A = 0.5190

[KCl]	$\frac{c = [Ba^{2+}]}{\times 10^3}$	$\frac{c' = [HClO_4]}{\times 10}$	pH	$\frac{\mu = [KCl] + 4c - c' + 2[H^+]}{}$	$8A\sqrt{\mu}$	$\frac{c_1 = [HX^-]}{\times 10^4}$	$\frac{\log c(c-c_1)}{}$	$\frac{\log c(c-c_1) - 8A\sqrt{\mu}}{}$
0.00	0.908	4.0	4.7	0.0032744	0.2375	3.576	$\bar{7}\cdot6985$	$\bar{7}\cdot461$
0.01	1.080	4.0	4.7	0.013965	0.4904	3.550	$\bar{7}\cdot8938$	$\bar{7}\cdot403$
0.02	1.172	4.0	4.7	0.0243344	0.6477	3.536	$\bar{7}\cdot9817$	$\bar{7}\cdot334$
0.03	1.256	4.0	4.7	0.0346716	0.7731	3.524	$\bar{6}\cdot0552$	$\bar{7}\cdot282$
0.04	1.328	4.0	4.7	0.0449644	0.8802	3.516	$\bar{6}\cdot1127$	$\bar{7}\cdot233$
0.05	1.400	4.0	4.7	0.0552492	0.9757	3.508	$\bar{6}\cdot1670$	$\bar{7}\cdot191$
0.06	1.452	4.0	4.7	0.065458	1.0621	3.500	$\bar{6}\cdot2041$	$\bar{7}\cdot142$
0.07	1.504	4.0	4.7	0.0756666	1.1422	3.494	$\bar{6}\cdot2398$	$\bar{7}\cdot098$
0.08	1.545	4.0	4.7	0.0858312	1.2165	3.488	$\bar{6}\cdot2667$	$\bar{7}\cdot050$

Of the parameters involved in equation (7a), c was experimentally determined by direct titration, c_1 , however, was equal to $[HClO_4]_T - [H^+]$. $[H^+]$ was obtained from pH measurement and the activity coefficient of H^+ in solution. Since pH measurements could be taken only correct to 0.05 units, $[H^+]$ was subject to an error, in some cases, upto $\pm 12\%$. A difference of 12% in actual $[H^+]$ and assumed $[H^+]$ gives a $\log K_{sp}$ value ± 0.004 , or a difference of about 1%.

If we consider $[H^+]$ to be negligible then, $[HClO_4]_T = [HX^-] = c'$ and hence $[X^{2-}] = c - c'$ and so (7a) can be written as,

$$\log c(c-c') - 8A\sqrt{\mu} = \log K_{sp} - B\mu \quad \dots (7b)$$

and the ionic strength, μ , then will be equal to,

$$\mu = 4[Ba^{2+}] - [HClO_4]_T + [KCl]_T \quad \dots (8)$$

instead of that given in equation (3). A plot of $\log c(c-c') - 8A\sqrt{\mu}$ against μ again gives a straight line. Using the method of least squares the intercept on the ordinate, which equals $\log K_{sp}$, is found to be $\bar{7}\cdot434$ at 35°. The value of $\log K_{sp_1}$ ignoring $[H^+]$ and $\log K_{sp_2}$, taking $[H^+]$ into account at different temperatures, are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

7 + Log Ksp of BaX at different temperatures

Temp. °C	25	35	45	55	65	75
Log $K_{sp_1} + 7$ ignoring $[H^+]$	0.297	0.434	0.468	0.509	0.526	0.558
Log $K_{sp_2} + 7$ taking $[H^+]$ in account	0.339	0.461	0.490	0.515	0.549	0.558
B obtained from Fig. 1	4.63	4.85	4.92	3.59	5.21	5.61

It is seen that at all temperatures $\log K_{sp_1}$ is lower than $\log K_{sp_2}$. This is clearly due to systematic error introduced due to neglecting $[H^+]$. The error becomes less and less as temperature is increased. The values of Ksp which we consider to be more accurate are when $[H^+]$ is taken into account.

The accuracy of $\log K_{sp_2}$ values obtained at 25° and 35° was also tested in another way. The second dissociation constant of Oxalic acid, is given by the equation,

$$K_2 = \frac{[H^+][X^{2-}]}{[HX^-]} \frac{f_+ \cdot f_{2-}}{f_-} \quad (9)$$

where f_s are the activity coefficient of the ionic species. Upto $\mu = 0.1$ as considered in these experiments f_+ can be taken to be equal to f_- . Introduction of equation (1) and (2) in equation (9) above gives

$$\begin{aligned} K_2 &= f_{2-} \left\{ \frac{([HClO_4]_T - [HX^-])([Ba^{2+}] - [HX^-])}{[HX^-]} \right\} \\ &= f_{2-} \left\{ \frac{[HClO_4]_T \cdot [Ba^{2+}]}{[HX^-]} - ([HClO_4]_T + [Ba^{2+}] + [HX^-]) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

If now we assume $f_{SO_4} = f_{2-}$ upto $\mu = 0.085$, we can get values of f_{2-} from the equation for f_{SO_4} given by Sharma and Prasad⁹. The values of K_2 of oxalic acid has been measured by Harned and Fallon¹⁰. Solving the above quadratic equation, we get $[HX^-]$. From the equation $[Ba^{2+}] = [X^{2-}] + [HX^-]$, we now find $[X^{2-}]$ from our measurements. From equation (6), we see

$$\log K_{sp} - B\mu = \log [Ba^{2+}] + \log [X^{2-}] - 8A\sqrt{\mu}$$

A plot of R.H.S. of this equation against μ gives a straight line, the intercept of which on the ordinate gives $\log K_{sp}$. $\log K_{sp}$ thus found at 25° and 35° are 7.341 and 7.463 respectively. These values agree with our K_{sp_2} values.

Fig. 1 gives the plot of $\log c(c-c') - 8A\sqrt{\mu}$ (i.e., when $[H^+]$ is taken into account), against μ at 25°, 35°, 45°, 55°, 65° and 75°. The slope of the curves gives the respective B and are recorded in Table 2.

The heat of solution, ΔH , of Barium Oxalate is related to $\log K_{sp}$ by the equation

$$\log K_{sp} = \frac{-\Delta H}{2.303RT} + \text{const.} \quad \dots (10)$$

Fig. 2 shows the plot of $\log K_{sp}$ against $1/T$ which is apparently not linear and is perhaps made up of two smooth curves meeting at about 55° . ΔH changes with temperature. Assuming ΔH to be almost constant over a ten degree rise in temperature, its value has been calculated from equation (10) and recorded in Table 3 below, rounded off to the nearest 0.1 K.cal.

TABLE 3

Heat of solution of Barium Oxalate at different temperatures

Temp.	(25-35) 30°	(35-45) 40°	(45-55) 50°	(55-65) 60°	(65-75) 70°
ΔH , Cals.	5.1	1.3	1.2	2.0	0.5

ΔH values are found to be positive throughout between 25° - 75° .

Barium Oxalate is known to form several hydrates^{1,11,12}. In solid phase, upto 40° , we are sure that we are dealing with $BaX \cdot 2H_2O$. The breaks in the values of ΔH and abrupt change in B indicates that there may be other hydrates also. The big change in ΔH with change in temperature suggests change in the hydration of the solid phase.

Fig 2
PLOT OF LOG K_{sp} AGAINST $1/T$

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